

2014

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education
Research Journal (AMIERJ)***

***(Bi-Monthly)
Peer-Reviewed Journal
Impact factor: 0.948***

VOL - III Issues: V

***Chief-Editor:
Ubale Amol Baban***

30/11/2014

**AN ANALYSIS OF ATTITUDE OF B-SCHOOL FACULTY MEMBERS
TOWARDS FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION**

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Abstract

Management institutes a part of higher education system, determine the career paths of the youth and in turn the future of the country. Students, parents, teachers, staff and society in general are the stakeholders of these institutes. Faculty members, the core eighty percent human resource of any management institute, have the potential and power to transform the future generation of a country. This paper studies and identifies the affective, cognitive and conative factors which drive job satisfaction of management faculty members and is directed towards understanding the factors which affects to job satisfaction of faculty members at management institutes in Pune, in the state of Maharashtra.

Key words

Job satisfaction, management faculty, B-school faculty, management faculty in Pune, attitude

INTRODUCTION

“Teaching is a profession that lies at the heart of both the learning of children and young people and their social, cultural and economic development. It is crucial to transmitting and implanting social values, such as democracy equality, tolerance cultural understanding, and respect for each person’s fundamental freedoms.” (“Building the Future through Quality

Education.” Policy Paper on Education adoptedunanimously at the 6th Education International World Congress 2011.)

The quality and achievements of academic complements determine the quality of management education programs, management research, and the perception of schools in academic as well as business environments(Lorange , 2003). Management institutes a part of higher education system, determine the career paths of the youth and in turn the future of the country. Students, parents, teachers, staff and society in general are the stakeholders of these institutes. Faculty members, the core eighty percent human resource of any management institute, have the potential and power to transform the future generation of a country.

Over the years, the number of management institutes in India has increased manifold and so have the number of student enrollments. However, this growth in terms of numbers has not been coupled with proportionate number of faculty members. Most of the higher educational institutes throughout the country are suffering from acute shortage of faculty, and specially good faculty members.

With the copiousness of job opportunities available to employees in the job market, a constant challenge faced by management is related to the retention of existing employees. The Finance Minister, ArunJaitley, made an announcement of setting up of new IIMs in his 2013 Budget speech. These five new IIMs would be established in the states of Himachal Pradesh, Punjab, Bihar, Odisha and Maharashtra.(Hindustan Times, July 10, 2014). An IIM in Maharashtra would bring with it multiple stakes and opportunities for multiple stakeholders, especially, the faculty members of the top ten management institutions in terms of another good job opportunity. According to the Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Human Resource Development MHRD, educational sector has witnessed a tremendous increase in its institutional capacity since independence. Varied reasons drive faculty members to leave education for industry or even the present institution for another. The reasons could be for better offer, or dissatisfaction with the management or the failure of the institute to manage job satisfaction, and

the like. Lack of job satisfaction is a predictor of quitting a job (Alexander, Lichtenstein and Hellmann, 1997; Jamal, 1997). Sometimes workers may quit from public to the private sector and vice versa. At the other times the movement is from one profession to another that is considered a greener pasture. A study of literature testifies that good administrators apparently realize that a high rate of turnover of faculty members results in a faculty of limited commitment, ineffective curriculum development, and general faculty unrest, and it can be costly both to the reputation of the institution and to the well-being of the students (Nicholson and Miljus, 1972). The health of an educational institution depends on the job satisfaction of its employees (Wood, 1976).

The scope of this paper lies in identifying the affective, cognitive and conative factors which drive job satisfaction of management faculty members and is directed towards understanding the factors which affects to job satisfaction of faculty members at management institutes in Pune, in the state of Maharashtra.

Literature Review

Job Satisfaction

A review of the literature indicates that job satisfaction is a prerequisite to long tenure and good performance, and hence to institutional effectiveness (Wood, 1976). It has been characterized by researchers as essential to organizational performance (Mathieu, 1991; Ostroff, 1992) Quality in teaching and learning can only be enhanced if the faculty members are satisfied and content (Chen, et al. 2006). Job satisfaction is defined as a general behavior towards an object or job (Okpara, 2006), "the extent to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs" (Spector, 1997, p. 2). Okoye (2011) viewed job satisfaction as how contented an individual is with his or her job. Obineli (2010) opined job satisfaction as an affective or emotional response towards various facets of one's job. Job satisfaction reflects how content employees are with the job and their reactions toward their work experiences (Berry, 1997), emotional state or reactions toward the job (Gruneberg, 1979; Landy and Conte, 2004), how positive people feel about their jobs, aspects of their job (Spector, 1997) and work situations

(Wood, Wood and Boyd, 2007). It is the function of the degree to which one's needs can be satisfied (Glimmer, 1966).

Schultz and Schultz (1998) emphasized that people spend one third to one half of their waking hours at work, for a period of 40 to 45 years, and that this is a very long time to be frustrated, dissatisfied and unhappy, especially since these feelings carry over to family and social life, and affect physical and emotional health. According to (Mitchell and Lasan, 1987), it is generally recognized in the organizational behaviour field that job satisfaction is the most important and frequently studied attitude. Locke and Lathan (1976) give a comprehensive definition of job satisfaction as pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experience.

A better understanding of job satisfaction and factors associated with it is helpful to guide employees' activities in a desired direction. Satisfaction is a relevant measure because many studies have demonstrated that other factors being equal, satisfied individuals are likely to be willing to exert more effort than unsatisfied individuals (Bryant, 2006; Özgüngör, 2010). The literature indicates that job satisfaction is a prerequisite to an educator's long tenure and performance, and overall institutional effectiveness (Wood, 1976). For these reasons it seems wise to identify factors that affect job satisfaction of faculty members within an educational institution. Job satisfaction is not only an indicator of overall individual well-being (Diaz-Serrano and Cabral Vieira, 2005), but also a good predictor of intentions or decisions of employees to leave a job (Gazioglu and Tansel, 2002). The most valuable information to have regarding an employee in an organization is a validated measure of his/her level of job satisfaction (Roznowski and Hulin 1992). Job satisfaction is regarded as related to important employee and organizational outcomes, ranging from job performance to health and longevity (Spector, 2003). The nature of the environment outside of the job directly influences a person's feelings and behavior on the job (Hadebe, 2001). Schultz and Schultz (1998) held the view that job satisfaction encompasses the positive and negative feelings and attitudes people hold about their

jobs, and that these depend on many work-related characteristics, but also on personal characteristics, such as age, gender, health and social relationships.

Adeyemo's (2000) considered that job satisfaction on a job might be motivated by the nature of the job, its pervasive social climate and extent to which workers peculiar needs are met. These factors found an echo in the works of other researchers too (Armentor, Forsyth, 1995, Flanagan, Johnson and Berret, 1996; Kadushin, and Kulys, 1995). There are factors like availability of power and status, pay satisfaction, promotion opportunities, and task clarity (Bolarin, 1993; Gomez-Hernandez, Max, Kosier, Paradiso and Robinson, 1997) which have been discussed by researchers at length. Other researchers (e.g. MacDonald, 1996; O'Toole, 1980) argued in favour of the control of job satisfaction by factors intrinsic to the workers. Their arguments are based on the idea that workers deliberately decide to find satisfaction in their jobs and perceive them as worthwhile.

In this paper, cognitive information is based on the experience of the respondents in their respective institute. The research work will identify the cognitive, affective and conative factors impacting the job satisfaction of the faculty members in B schools.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objectives for the present study are:

1. Measuring the validity of job satisfaction factors for faculty members teaching in MBA programme of colleges and universities in Pune.
2. Identifying the Affective, Cognitive and Conative Factors influencing job satisfaction of faculty members teaching in MBA programme of colleges and universities in Pune.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research study adopted the descriptive research design. Data were obtained through primary sources and secondary sources. Primary data was collected through questionnaire

method and expert opinion while secondary data was collected through review of literature. Faculty members in the MBA colleges and MBA departments of universities in Pune were the respondents. The sample size is 104, obtained through simple random sampling method, from primary sources. Reliability test was conducted. The number of items in the questionnaire were twenty-five, and on running SPSS, the Cronbach's Alpha was 0.798.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.798	25

RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS .

The researchers surveyed 104 faculty members from 20 management institutions in Pune city for the survey. For the purpose of collecting data, researchers used web based and hard copies of questionnaire, and few expert opinions through emails. To monitor the job satisfaction factors, 25 factors were identified from review of literature and this research work was considered to suffice as pilot survey to check the validity and authenticity of factors. In order to analyze the factors impacting the job satisfaction of the faculty members, researchers performed factor analysis on SPSS. The extraction method used was principle component analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
VAR00003	-.078	.735	-.028	.111	-.215	-.005	.169	.141
VAR00012	.039	.756	.189	-.001	.004	-.150	-.058	-.232
VAR00016	.419	.605	.216	-.273	.137	.083	-.217	.175
VAR00017	.193	.454	-.054	.144	.108	.383	.152	.435
VAR00018	.106	.805	-.033	-.041	.034	.075	-.118	.131

VAR00001	.108	-.114	-.015	.707	.273	.174	.134	.069
VAR00002	.136	.196	-.038	.513	-.208	-.246	.025	.022
VAR00004	-.074	-.043	-.029	.163	-.018	.919	-.033	-.003
VAR00005	.228	.035	.067	-.140	.130	.816	.040	-.143
VAR00006	-.012	-.112	.024	.139	.825	.206	.188	.063
VAR00007	-.130	-.011	.816	-.083	.204	.018	.075	.316
VAR00008	.659	-.190	.006	.388	.129	.232	.325	.129
VAR00009	.696	.136	.036	.386	-.169	-.037	.030	.054
VAR00010	.043	.343	.602	.491	.192	.005	-.033	-.025
VAR00011	.483	.278	.225	.173	.381	-.214	.067	-.006
VAR00013	.408	.512	.037	.005	.537	-.104	.039	-.224
VAR00014	.713	.126	-.129	.003	.444	-.012	.266	-.031
VAR00015	.798	.102	-.027	.071	-.068	.146	.074	.181
VAR00019	.439	-.116	-.215	.673	.139	.108	-.092	-.065
VAR00020	.178	.082	.112	.021	-.029	-.122	-.029	.798
VAR00021	.271	.087	.504	-.237	-.189	.103	-.343	-.040
VAR00022	.111	-.069	.402	.204	.178	.050	.685	-.175
VAR00023	-.072	.038	.688	-.169	-.425	-.066	.227	-.205
VAR00024	.311	.047	-.030	-.042	.014	.052	.823	.068
VAR00025	-.066	-.122	-.173	-.044	.412	-.205	.557	.480

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 12 iterations.

The results from the analysis clearly indicated out of 25 components, 3 are the most critical components. Scale reliability is operationalized as internal consistency, which is the degree of intercorrelations among the items that constitute the scale (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). A value of Cronbach's alpha of 0.6 or more is used as a criterion for a reliable scale (Hair et al., 1998; Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). CR value higher than 0.6 implies that there is high internal consistency (Fornell and Bookstein 1982). Opportunities for research, training and

development, organizational culture and teaching climate emerged as the cognitive factors ; attitude of management towards faculty members; inter-personal relationships at work; passion for teaching; respect & recognition; trust on the brand were classified as the affective factors and better job opportunity and word of mouth were the factors which were grouped as the conative factors. In the study of social psychology Thomas & Znaniecki, 1918; had assumed that attitude was the key to understanding human behavior . In order to have systematic investigation of the attitude–behavior relation with the job satisfaction this study was conducted. To accomplish its objectives, this study utilized attitude formation theory presented by Eagly and Chaiken (1993). Their model suggests that individuals’ attitudes are formed primarily or exclusively on the basis of any one of three types of components: cognitive, affective, and conative. Cognitive factors are created when individuals gain information about the attitude object and thereby form beliefs (Ajzen and Fishbein 1975, Eagly and Chaiken 1993) This information (knowledge) is gained by direct experience (participation, involvement) and indirect experience with objects (Simmons and Lynch 1991). As Eagly and Chaiken (1993) suggest, an affective factor is based on emotional experiences or preferences. Both positive (e.g., delight) and negative affect (e.g., anger) can arise from experiences with the organization. A conative factor is connected to a person’s overt actions in relation to the attitude object (Eagly and Chaiken 1993).

Cognitive Factors	Factors	Variables	Cronbach Alpha
	Opportunities for research	VAR00008	0.804
	Opportunities for Training & Development	VAR00009	
	Organizational Culture	VAR00014	
	Teaching Climate	VAR00015	
Affective Factors	Attitude of management towards faculty members	VAR00003	0.773
	Inter-personal relationships at work	VAR00012	

	Passion for teaching	VAR00013	
	Respect & recognition	VAR00016	
	Trust on the brand	VAR00018	
Conative Factors	Better job opportunity	VAR00004	0.796
	Word of mouth	VAR00005	

LIMITATIONS

One of the most important factors impacting the job satisfaction is salary. In order to avoid any biased opinion in the survey, salary has not been considered as one of the factors impacting satisfaction. Another major limitation of this study is that it may not be appropriate to generalize its findings, owing to the small sample size and study area being limited only to Pune district. Also, the data obtained through questionnaires were all self-reports from the participants hence the findings may be subject to response consistency effect. This study is to be considered as an indicator of the

CONCLUSION

For further research, AHP analysis is recommended which would reconfirm the factors impacting job satisfaction and also rank them in priority. Another research which focuses on faculty need for professional growth and research opportunities is proposed. Teacher job satisfaction is often cited and rendered important in both research on teacher attrition and teacher retention (Voke, 2002; Stockard & Lehman, 2004). Managing talent and enabling them to develop feelings of belongingness and of value towards institution is crucial. A study on how to attract talent to the field of education while making education sector attractive for them would contribute to the body of research related to this field. Understanding factors affecting job satisfaction is one way to delve into the minds of teachers in the education sector. A study on whether the factors affecting job satisfaction of management teachers can be used to make the education sector on the whole an attractive magnet that pulls the best of minds towards this noble profession from all domains and sectors would add a new dimension to the existing body of literature.

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